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**INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY COMPETENCIES NEEDED BY BUSINESS
EDUCATION GRADUATES IN GOMBE STATE**

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Abstract

The study was aimed at identifying the ICT competencies needed by Business Education graduates in the labour market. Two formulated research questions and two hypotheses guides the study. A descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The population comprised 22 lecturers all drawn from the Federal University of Kashere, Business Education Department of Federal College of Technical, Gombe. There was no sample of the study as the population is manageable in size. A self-structured questionnaire of 4 rating scale was used to collect data from respondents. The instrument was validated by 3 experts and was tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient which yielded 0.78. Mean and Standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. While t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings indicated that for Business Education Graduates to be valuable in the labour market, they should acquire basic computer and Internet skills. Also, both male and female Business Education Graduates can acquire ICT skills and become competent on these skills without any segregation. It was recommended among others that Business Education Graduates should be taught internet related skills to enable them develop needed competencies in internet.

Keywords: ICT, Competencies, Business Education Graduates

Introduction

Technology and information surround everyone, no matter who they are, where they live or what they do for a living. ICT is an acronym that stands for Information Communications Technology. It is always a difficult task to define ICT because the concepts, methods and applications involved in ICT are constantly evolving on an almost daily basis and it is difficult to keep up with these changes as they happen so fast. However, Mbam (2010) defined Information and Communication Technology as the technique employed in acquiring, processing, storage and dissemination of audio, video, pictorial, textual and other discrete information with the aids of electronics computing devices and telecommunication gadgets. He further stated that it actually combines computing with high-speed communication links carrying information of differing sorts as sound, video, text or ordinary image. Technologies such as cell phones, pagers fax machines, and portable computer has reduced the meaning attached to physical locations in terms of time, work, and leisure to mere formalities. Furthermore,

Apagu and Wakili 2015 posited that ICT are increasingly playing an important role in organizations and in society's ability to produce, access, adopt and apply information.

The role of ICT in the school as well as business cannot be undermined. It can be utilized in a classroom setting to enhance curricula relevance and adoption. In the assertion of Akpan (2018), ICT utilization in teaching is capable of yielding the following dividends:

- learners are provided with immediate access to richer source of materials
- Provide information in new and relevant ways, which helps learners to understand, assimilate and use it more readily.
- ICT utilization in teaching motivate and stimulate learning
- enhances learning for learners with special needs
- motivate learners to try out new ideas and take risk
- ICT encourages teachers to take fresh look at how they teach and ways in which students learn.
- ICT utilization sharpens learners' attention and also offers potentials for effective group and individual work.

More so, ICT can play a significant role in the business world. Oduma (2010) stated that employers of labour are desirous of employing graduates with professional business soft skills or competencies as a pre-condition for gainful employment. He further stated that, it is the evolution and advancement in ICT which is fast becoming the life-wire of all viable organizations both at national and international levels that has spurred the ideas of acquiring personnel with business soft skills or competencies.

Competencies in the use of ICT is very important. In this study, competencies are seen as sets of demonstrable characteristics, ability and skills that enable professionals improve efficiency and performance of a job efficiently and effectively. To be competent, somebody must be able to react to a situation and follow behaviours you have found to succeed in the past. To do this, you must have repertoire of possible actions to take and training in them, because competency grows only with experience and training. Indeed, Oduma (2010) stressed that becoming competent at a given skill, allows one to perform a task with ease, boosting productivity and increasing performance in the work place.

Business education is a programme of study that places more emphasis on competencies. It is designed to offers students who wish to pursue a career in business an opportunity to develop those skills, abilities and understanding that will enable them to enter, perform and progress in a business occupation after graduating from high school or the university. Osuala (2018) sees business education as a programme of instruction which consist of two points, office education and general business education that provide students with information and experiences which are needed by all in managing personal business affair and using the services of the business. In essence, Business Education inculcate necessary knowledge, competencies, experiences and right attitude needed in the labour market.

There are many areas of competencies need in relation to ICT. Ezenwafor in Emeasoba, and Nweke (2016) mentioned some of these competencies to include the ability: to use of microcomputer with software application to produce a document, Skilful keyboarding, using broad cast material or CD ROM for information collection and storage; E-mailing and messaging; Internet browsing using search engines, window messenger, yahoo chartrooms; Using projectors, slide and multimedia projector for presentation among others.

This study focusses on the use of computer and the Internet competencies which have become unavoidable tools in the success of modern businesses. Computer is an electronic machine or device, capable of accepting data, processing data and produce the output in a specified format. According to the Ezeali and Ehilia in Ammani (2014), computer is an electronic

device which accepts information from an input device analyzes it through a processor and stores or transfers it accordingly to the output device for printing purposes. This means that a computer is a device manufactured to accept an ordered sequence of instructions given to it in an appropriate language and to carry out these instructions with great speed and accuracy, You can also access Internet and send E-mail through several channels, so long as you have a computer and the modern device that links your computer to the telephone line.

Statement of the Problem

Computer and Internet are very vital in the 21st century computer wise. Both public and private sectors are in the state of art in terms of office operations, therefore, they need to employ competent office managers to handle their database. But unfortunately, Many OTM graduates in the labour market are not competent enough (Oduma, 2010). This could be due to the training they received during their school time where some of the institutions lacks ICT facilities to give adequate training to their students. Subsequent upon this, the research deemed fit to conduct the research in order to find out the competencies needed by OTM graduates in the labour market. There are many areas of competencies need in relation to ICT. Ezenwafor in Emeasoba, and Nweke (2016) mentioned some of these competencies to include the ability: to use of microcomputer with software application to produce a document, Skilful keyboarding, using broad cast material or CD ROM for information collection and storage; E-mailing and messaging; Internet browsing using search engines, window messenger, yahoo chartrooms; Using projectors, slide and multimedia projector for presentation among others.

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Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to identify the ICT competencies needed by Business Education Graduates in Gombe state the labour market. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the computer competencies needed by business education graduates in the labour market.
2. Ascertain the internet competencies needed by Business education graduates in the labour market.

Research Questions

The study was guided by two research questions:

1. What are the computer competencies needed by Business Education Graduates in Gombe State?
2. What are the internet competencies needed by Business Education graduates in Gombe State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- HO1** There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on computer competences needed in Gombe state based on gender.
- HO2** There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on internet competences needed in Gombe state based on working experience.

Methodology

The descriptive survey design was used to carry out this study. The study was conducted in Gombe State. The population was made up of 22 respondents both male and females who are Business educators at Federal University of Kashere and Federal College of Education, Technical Gombe, Gombe State. There was no sample or sampling, because the population was manageable. 4-points rating scale structured questionnaire was developed by the researcher as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) 4 points, Agree (A) 3 points, Disagree (D) 2 points, Strongly Disagree (SD)1 point. Also, the instrument contains 25 items. Two research questions and two hypotheses are formulated to guide the study. Descriptive statistics using Mean and Standard Deviation were adopted to answer the research questions, while t-test was used at 0.05 Alpha level of significance in testing the null hypotheses. Also, the instrument contains 25 items.

Results

Research Questions 1: What are the computer competencies needed by Business Education Graduates in the labour market?

Table 1: Mean rating and Standard Deviation of the Responses on the computer competencies needed by Business Education Graduates in the labour market

S/N	ITEMS STATEMENT	N	MEAN	STD	DECISION
1.	Keyboarding skill	22	3.77	0.42	Strongly Agree
2.	Editing skill	22	3.81	0.39	Strongly Agree
3.	Skill in Data processing	22	3.45	0.50	Agree
4.	Saving & retrieving document	22	2.86	0.46	Agree
5.	Search and replace words	22	2.72	0.45	Agree
6.	Copy and paste	22	3.45	0.50	Agree
7.	Insert and remove	22	3.31	0.47	Agree
8.	Word wrapping	22	2.72	0.45	Agree
9.	Insert footer	22	3.09	0.68	Agree
10.	Insert header	22	2.72	0.45	Agree
11.	Formatting Skill	22	3.72	0.45	Strongly Agree
12.	page numbering	22	2.81	0.50	Agree
	Grand Mean		3.20		Agree

On table 1 above, the respondents strongly agreed to item 1, 2 and 11 while the rest of the items were agreed to as computer competencies needed by business education graduates in the labour market. Also, the grand mean value of 3.20 which was greater than the criteria mean value of 2.50 revealed that items fit into computer competencies needed by Business Education graduates in the labour market.

Research Question 2: What are the internet competencies needed by Business education graduates in the labour market?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Responses on the Internet competencies needed by Business Education Graduates in the labour market

S/N	Items Statement	N	MEAN	STD	DECISION
13.	Ability to share online materials	22	3.77	0.42	Strongly Agree
14.	Ability to use bookmark/favourites	22	2.86	0.46	Agree
15.	E-marketing skills	22	2.81	0.50	Agree
16.	Web analytics skill	22	2.54	0.50	Agree
17.	Ability to use social media	22	3.68	0.47	Strongly Agree
18.	Ability to navigate on the web browser	22	3.68	0.47	Strongly Agree
19	Capable of locating web address	22	2.81	0.39	Agree
20.	Ability in Electronic fund transfer	22	3.81	0.39	Strongly Agree
21.	Transactions in buying and selling online	22	2.86	0.46	Agree
22.	Ability to use hyperlink	22	2.72	0.55	Agree
23.	Ability to in send & receive mails in social media Apps	22	3.45	0.50	Agree
24.	Skill in e-learning capabilities	22	3.81	0.39	Strongly Agree
25.	Ability to shop online	22	2.54	0.50	Agree
	Grand Mean		3.18		Agree

In table 2, the respondents strongly agreed to items 13, 17, 18, 20, and 24, and agreed with other items as internet competencies needed by business education graduates in the labour market. The grand mean of 3.18 confirmed the respondents, in all agreed with the items as needed internet competencies in the labour market.

Research Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on computer competences needed in the labour market based on gender.

Table 3: t-test analysis on computer competences needed in the labour market based on gender

DF = 20								
S/N	ITEMS STATEMENT	Gender	N	Mean	Std	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
1	Keyboarding skill	Male	13	3.84	0.37	0.96	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	3.66	0.50			
2	Editing skill	Male	13	3.76	0.43	0.69	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	3.88	0.33			
3	Skill in Data processing	Male	13	3.46	0.51	0.75	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	3.44	0.52			
4	Saving & retrieving document	Male	13	2.76	0.43	1.14	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	3.00	0.50			
5	Search and replace words	Male	13	2.69	0.48	0.42	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	2.77	0.44			
6	Copy and paste	Male	13	3.46	0.51	0.07	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	3.44	0.52			
7	Insert and remove	Male	13	3.30	0.48	0.12	2.08	Accepted
		Female	9	3.33	0.50			
8	Word wrapping	Male	13	2.69	0.48	0.42	2.08	Accepted

9	Insert footer	Female	9	2.77	0.44	0.74	2.08	Accepted
		Male	13	3.00	0.70			
10	Insert header	Female	9	3.22	0.66	0.51	2.08	Accepted
		Male	13	2.76	0.43			
11	Formatting Skill	Female	9	2.66	0.50	0.51	2.08	Accepted
		Male	13	3.76	0.43			
12	Page numbering	Female	9	3.66	0.50	0.54	2.08	Accepted
		Male	13	2.76	0.43			
		Female	9	2.88	0.60			

In table 3 above, revealed that, the calculated grand mean of (0.47) was less than the t-critical value (2.08). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted and concludes that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on computer competences needed in the labour market based on gender.

Research Hypotheses 2: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on internet competences needed in the labour market based on working experience.

Table 4: t-test analysis on internet competences needed in the labour market based on working experience. DF=20

S/N	Items Statement	Work Experience	N	Mean	Std	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
13	Ability to share online materials	Below 15 years	7	3.85	0.37	0.62	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	3.73	0.45			
14	Ability to use bookmark/favourites	Below 15 years	7	3.00	0.57	0.93	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.80	0.41			
15	E-marketing skills	Below 15 years	7	2.85	0.37	0.24	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.80	0.56			
16	Web analytics skill	Below 15 years	7	2.42	0.53	0.72	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.60	0.50			
17	Ability to use social media	Below 15 years	7	3.57	0.53	0.73	2.08	Accepted
		Ability to navigate on the web browser	16 years Above	15	3.73			
18	Capable of locating web address	Below 15 years	7	3.57	0.53	0.73	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	3.73	0.45			
19	Ability in Electronic fund transfer	Below 15 years	7	2.85	0.37	0.30	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.80	0.41			
20	Transactions in buying and selling online	Below 15 years	7	3.85	0.37	0.30	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	3.80	0.41			
21	Ability to use hyperlink	Below 15 years	7	2.71	0.48	1.02	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.93	0.45			
22	Ability to in send & receive mails in social media Apps	Below 15 years	7	2.71	0.75	0.07	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.73	0.45			
23	Skill in e-learning capabilities	Below 15 years	7	3.42	0.53	0.15	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	3.46	0.51			
24	Ability to shop online	Below 15 years	7	3.88	0.33	0.69	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	3.76	0.43			
25		Below 15 years	7	2.42	0.53	0.72	2.08	Accepted
		16 years Above	15	2.60	0.50			

In table 4 above, revealed that the calculated grand mean of (0.56) was less than the t-critical value (2.08). Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. The researcher concludes that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on internet competences needed in the labour market based on working experience.

Discussion of Results

Findings in table 1 suggested that computer competencies are needed by Business Education Graduates in the labour market agreed by the respondents. Similarly, table 3 revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on computer competences needed in the labour market based on gender. The findings are in consonant with the study of Mafikuyomi (2016), who revealed that the ICT skills training that are highly needed by Business Education Students for entrepreneurship development includes: basic computer knowledge, deleting documents, printing document, creating, viewing, retrieving, saving document from the computer and more.

Table 2 indicated that internet competencies are needed in the labour market. Similarly, Table 4 revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of Business Education graduates on internet skills competences needed in the labour market based on working experience. The findings are in line with Mafikuyomi (2016) found that, downloading information from the internet, accessing the internet, assessing e-mail, using excel for calculations, using software, uploading information, product awareness etc are essential competencies. The findings are equally supported by Elizabeth and Oyedele (2016) that, internet, video and audio transfer solutions, emails, phones, ability to create, save, and forward data and information and all-important components of such technology are required competencies in business.

Conclusion

This paper focused on the Information technology competencies needed by Business Education Graduates in the labour market. The impacts of ICT to Business Education Graduates in the labour market cannot be over emphasized. Nowadays, no organization can think of administering its affairs in achieving their goal and objectives in the world of work, without having very effective and efficient computer literate workers including business education graduates who are to handle all business administrative matters of the organization. As such, there is need to undergo a thorough training in order to acquire internet and computer competences. Therefore, there is need for business education graduates to be competent in computer and internet, so that they can be employed in the labour market. Anyone without these skills to display in the world of business, subsequently, will be dumped.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Business Education Graduates should acquire basic computer skills to enhance their competitiveness in the labour market.
2. Business Education Graduates should be taught internet related skills to enable them develop needed competencies in internet.

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